

Synthesis, crystal structures and magnetic characterization of two *trans*-dicyanoiron(III)-based ion-pair complexes

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Abstract : Two *trans*-dicyanometalates-based Fe^{III}-Ni^{II} ion-pair complexes with the formula [Fe(bpb)(CN)₂][NiL¹] \cdot 0.5CH₃CN \cdot H₂O (1) and {[Fe(bpb)(CN)₂]₂[Ni(L²)₂]} \cdot 5H₂O (2) has been obtained and characterized by element analysis and structure determination. (bpb²⁻ = 1,2-bis(pyridine-2-carboxamido)benzenate, L¹ = 11,13-dimethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclotrideca-10,12-diene, L² = diethylenetriamine). Single X-ray diffraction reveals their ion-pair structure containing the same *trans*-dicyanoiron(III) anion(s), for which are balanced by the Ni^{II} ion involved in slightly distorted square planar and octahedron for complexes 1 and 2, respectively. Magnetism characterization for these two compounds show the typical paramagnetic characteristic of the low-spin iron(III) ion and the high-spin Ni^{II} ion.

Keywords : *trans*-Dicyanoiron(III), synthesis, crystal structure, magnetic property.

Introduction

During the past several decades, cyanide-bridged complexes with various structures over a wide range of dimensionalities, including molecular clusters, 1D chains and 2D and 3D networks¹⁻¹⁶, have been extensively studied in the field of molecular magnetism because of the efficient propagation of cyanide bridge for magnetic coupling. The rational design of cyanide-bridged materials can be achieved following a building-block approach with the premeditated association of various complexes and capped polycyanidometallates [M(L)_x(CN)_y]^{Z-} (L = mono- or multi-dentate ligand). This strategy provides better control of the dimensionality of the final outcome when carefully selecting the building blocks with both the negative and neutral charged [M(L)_x(CN)_y]^{Z-} and other paramagnetic assemble segments.

In the several recent years, we have developed a series of cyanide-containing building blocks with two *trans* cyanide groups based-on quasi-planar tetradentate chelating pyridinecarboxamide ligand. Many cyanide-bridged magnetic complexes assembled from the reactions of these types of *trans*-dicyanometalates with other 3d transition metal compounds, such as Mn^{III}-Schiff base¹⁷⁻²⁰, Mn^{III}-porphyrin^{21,22}, polyimine-Ni^{II} compounds²³⁻²⁵, seven-coordinated Mn^{II} compounds^{26,27}, etc. have been reported.

For the purpose of obtaining more cyanide-bridged magnetic complexes resulted from this family of cyanide-predecessors, we investigated the reactions of K[Fe(bpb)(CN)₂] with the Ni^{II} compounds (Scheme 1). Unexpectedly, two Fe^{III}-Ni^{II} ion-pair complexes with no cyanide-bridges formulated as [Fe(bpb)(CN)₂][NiL¹] \cdot 0.5CH₃CN \cdot H₂O (1) and {[Fe(bpb)(CN)₂]₂[Ni(L²)₂]} \cdot 5H₂O (2) has been obtained, for which have been characterized by element analysis and structure determination. (bpb²⁻ = 1,2-bis(pyridine-2-carboxamido)benzenate, L¹ = 11,13-dimethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclotrideca-10,12-diene, L² = diethylenetriamine). This paper will mainly concern the synthesis, crystal structures and magnetic character of the above two complexes.

Scheme 1

Experimental

General procedures and materials : All the reactions were carried out under an air atmosphere and all chemicals and solvents used were reagent grade without further purification. The cyanide precursor $\text{K}[\text{Fe}(\text{bpb})(\text{CN})_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^1)]\text{ClO}_4$ was synthesized according to the reported method^{28,29}.

The preparation of complex 1 :

To a solution of $\text{K}[\text{Fe}(\text{bpb})(\text{CN})_2]$ (0.1 mmol, 46.5 mg) dissolved in methanol (10 ml) was added a solution of $[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^1)]\text{ClO}_4$ (0.1 mmol, 36.7 mg) in acetonitrile (10 ml). The mixture was stirred for several minutes before the undissolved materials were removed by filtration. The filtrate was allowed to slowly evaporate in air for about one week, and the dark-red crystals formed was collected by filtration. Yield : 53.3 mg, 73%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{36.5}\text{FeN}_{10.5}\text{NiO}_3$: C, 52.60; H, 5.03; N, 20.13. Found : C, 52.71; H, 5.28; N, 20.01.

The preparation of complex 2 :

The methanol solution (10 ml) containing $\text{K}[\text{Fe}(\text{bpb})(\text{CN})_2]$ (0.2 mmol, 93 mg) was added into another methanol solution (10 mL) formed *in situ* by $[\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (36.5 mg, 0.1 mmol) and diethylenetriamine (0.2 mol, 20.6 mg), and the mixture was stirred for about half an hour before the undissolved materials were removed by filtration. The filtrate was allowed to slowly evaporate in air for about two weeks, and the dark-red crystals formed was collected by filtration. Yield : 42 mg, 35%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{59}\text{Fe}_2\text{N}_{18}\text{NiO}_9$: C, 47.94; H, 4.95; N, 20.97. Found : C, 50.14; H, 5.33; N, 20.86.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses of carbon, hydrogen, and nitrogen were carried out with an Elementary Vario El. Variable-temperature magnetic susceptibility was performed on a Quantum Design MPMS SQUID magnetometer.

Structure determination :

Data were collected on a Oxford Diffraction Gemini E diffractometer with Mo $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) at 293 K. Final unit cell parameters were derived by global refinements of reflections obtained from integration of all the frame data. The collected frames were integrated by using the preliminary cell-orientation matrix. CrysAlisPro Agilent Technologies software was used for collecting

frames of data, indexing reflections, and determination of lattice constants; CrysAlisPro Agilent Technologies for integration of intensity of reflections and scaling, SCALE3 ABSPACK for absorption correction. The structures were solved by the direct method (SHELXS-97) and refined by full-matrix least-squares (SHELXL-97) on F^2 ³⁰. Anisotropic thermal parameters were used for the non-hydrogen atoms and isotropic parameters for the hydrogen atoms. Hydrogen atoms bonded to the C and N atoms were added geometrically and refined using a riding model. For those solvent H atoms, there were found from the Fourier map and some commands were used to rationalize the bond parameters. Crystallographic data and experimental details for structural analyses are summarized in Table 1. CCDC : 1407889-1407890.

Table 1. Crystallographic data and structure refinement summary for the compounds **1** and **2**

	1	2
Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{36.5}\text{FeN}_{10.5}\text{NiO}_3$	$\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{59}\text{Fe}_2\text{N}_{18}\text{NiO}_9$
Formula weight	730.78	1202.54
Crystal system	Triclinic	Orthorhombic
Space group	P-1	Pca2(1)
Unit cell dimensions (\AA)	$0.32 \times 0.25 \times 0.23$	$0.28 \times 0.22 \times 0.19$
<i>a</i> (\AA)	10.6602(9)	24.9884(16)
<i>b</i> (\AA)	11.8176(10)	11.1621(7)
<i>c</i> (\AA)	14.4933(13)	19.6216(13)
α (deg)	85.6990(10)	90
β (deg)	86.038(2)	90
γ (deg)	67.3370(10)	90
Volume (\AA^3)	1678.5(3)	5472.9(6)
Z	2	4
Calculated density (mg/m^3)	1.446	1.459
Absorption coefficient	1.043	0.934
<i>F</i> (000)	760	2500
Reflections/collected/unique	8371/5830/4538	31158/12238/7805
Data/restraints/parameters	5830/3/445	12238/0/703
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.054	0.996
Final <i>R</i> indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	0.0583	0.0574
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	0.1825	0.1663
Largest diff. peak and hole ($e/\text{\AA}^3$)	1.162 and -0.864	0.775 and -0.451

Results and discussion

Some important structural parameters for compounds **1** and **2** are collected in Table 2. The crystal structure and the cell packing diagram along *b* axis for complex **1** are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. For complex **2**, its crystal structure and one-dimensional supramolecular structure constructed by the intermolecular hydrogen bond interactions are given in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively.

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) for the compounds **1** and **2**

1		2	
Fe(1)-C(19)	1.979(5)	Fe(1)-C(1)	1.976(7)
Fe(1)-C(20)	1.969(5)	Fe(1)-C(2)	1.960(7)
Fe(1)-N(1)	1.898(3)	Fe(1)-N(3)	1.882(4)
Fe(1)-N(2)	1.898(3)	Fe(1)-N(4)	1.884(5)
Fe(1)-N(3)	2.005(3)	Fe(1)-N(5)	1.996(5)
Fe(1)-N(4)	1.975(4)	Fe(1)-N(6)	2.001(5)
Ni(1)-N(8)	1.816(6)	Ni(1)-N(13)	2.138(5)
Ni(1)-N(9)	1.888(5)	Ni(1)-N(14)	2.094(6)
Ni(1)-N(10)	1.905(6)	Ni(1)-N(15)	2.132(6)
Ni(1)-N(11)	1.811(4)	Ni(1)-N(16)	2.122(6)
		Ni(1)-N(17)	2.119(6)
		Ni(1)-N(18)	2.145(5)
N(5)-C(19)-Fe(1)	177.0(4)	N(1)-C(1)-Fe(1)	176.5(5)
N(6)-C(20)-Fe(1)	179.2(4)	N(2)-C(2)-Fe(1)	175.8(6)

Fig. 1. The molecular structure of complex **1**. The solvent molecules and all the h atoms have been omitted for clarity.

Fig. 2. The cell packing diagram along *b* axis of complex **1**.

Fig. 3. The molecular structure of complex **2**. The solvent molecules and all the h atoms have been omitted for clarity.

Fig. 4. The 1D supramolecular structure of complex **2** formed by intermolecular H-bond interactions.

As can be found in Table 2, these two complexes crystallize in triclinic space group *P*-1 and orthorhombic space group *Pca*2(1), respectively. The Fe atoms in these two complexes are coordinated by four N atoms of pyridinecarboxamide ligand locating in the equatorial plane and two C atoms of cyanide groups in *trans* position, forming a slightly distorted octahedral geometry. The Fe-N bond length is in the range of 1.882(4)–2.005(3) Å for these two compounds and the Fe-C_{cyanide} bond length is distributed to the narrow range of 1.960(7)–1.979(5) Å. The mean deviation of the plane formed by FeN₄ unit is 0.0258 and 0.0324 Å, and the Fe ion is only out of the plane 0.0013 and 0.0031 Å, respectively, indicating clearly that these five atoms are in a perfect equatorial plane. As listed in Table 2, the bond angle of Fe-C≡N in the realm of 175.8(6)–179.2(4)° demonstrates that the three atoms are in a good linear configuration.

The coordination sphere for the Ni^{II} ion in complex **1**, which coordinates to four N atoms from triethylenetetraamine, is square planar with a mean deviation from the plane formed by the Ni atom and four N atoms of 0.0917 Å. The four Ni^{II}-N bond lengths are with slight difference with the values of 1.816(6), 1.888(5), 1.905(6) and 1.811(4) Å, respectively. For, complex **2**, the Ni^{II} ion is six-coordinated, which is involved in an octahedron formed by six

Fig. 5. The temperature dependences of $\chi_M T$ of complexes **1** (left) and **2** (right).

N atoms from two diethylenetriamine molecules with the average Ni-N bond length of 2.125 Å. It should be pointed out, under the help of the intermolecular O...H...O and O...H...N hydrogen interactions, complex **2** can be linked into interesting one-dimensional supramolecular structure (Fig. 4).

The temperature dependence of magnetic susceptibility for complexes **1** and **2** measured in the range of 2–300 K under an external magnetic field of 2000 Oe are illustrated in Fig. 5. The change tendency of $\chi_M T$ - T curve for these two complexes is very similar to each other. The $\chi_M T$ values at room temperature are 1.39 and 1.79 emu K mol⁻¹ for complexes **1** and **2**, respectively, which is consistent with the spin only values of 1.375 and 1.75 emu K mol⁻¹ for one or two low-spin Fe^{III} ion and one high-spin Ni^{II} ion. With the temperature lowering, the $\chi_M T$ values keep almost constant up to about 50 K and then decreases with a high speed and reaches the value of about 0.51 and 0.65 emu K mol⁻¹ at 2 K, respectively. The decrease of the $\chi_M T$ value in the low temperature range can be attributed to the supramolecular magnetic interaction and/or the splitting of the Ni^{II} ion.

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